

ASSESSING THE CURRENT MAINTENANCE PRACTICE OF TECHNICAL COLLEGE BUILDINGS IN BAUCHI STATE

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Abstract

This study assessed the current maintenance practice of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State, Nigeria. The study was guided by one research question and corresponding hypothesis. Relevant literatures related to the research question were reviewed. The study adopted survey research design and total sample population was used for this study. Thirty-one respondents were used in the study comprising of Twenty-seven (27) administrators from the eight (8) Technical Colleges of Bauchi State (Principal and Vice Principals), Director/Deputy Directors science and technology of the Bauchi State Ministry of Education and four maintenance officers respectively. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire and was validated by three experts. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was found to be .875 and hence the instrument was found to be reliable. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 was used to analyse the data that was collected. The data obtained was analysed using Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation. Through the data collected for this study, it was discovered that all the Technical Colleges have no specific maintenance practices adopted for the maintenance of the buildings of the Bauchi State Technical Colleges. Based on the findings of this research, the researcher wishes to recommend that All Technical Colleges should adopt a specific maintenance practice for the maintenance College buildings in order to avoid the building collapsing on the students during teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Assessment, Maintenance Practice, Technical Colleges, Buildings

Introduction

It is noteworthy that decent school buildings enhance teaching and learning thereby making the process meaningful and purposeful. Thus School buildings are crucial because they foster effective pedagogy and boost good result (Iyamu, Imasuen, & Osakue, 2018). The quality and standard of a school is ideally rooted on the provision of sufficiency, operation and supervision of educational facilities. Looking at the deplorable state of public buildings across the country for decades, a large chunk of the country's resources has been channelled towards Transportation Infrastructure, Government administrative Buildings for ministries and Parastatals, Colleges of Education, Universities, Primary and Secondary Schools (Eke, Musa, Fashubaa, & Abass, 2017). In spite of millions of Naira

spent to erect all these buildings, they are left, as soon as commissioned to face premature but steady and rapid deterioration, decay and dilapidation (Adenuga, 2012).

Maintenance of school building is also required to serve staff and students well-being besides paying for the brick and mortar of the building. To this end effective school maintenance protects capital investment, ensures the health and safety of the students, and supports educational performance. It is noteworthy that decent school buildings enhance teaching and learning thereby making the process meaningful and purposeful. Therefore, School buildings are crucial because they foster effective pedagogy and boost good result (Iyamu *et al* 2018). It was further observed by (Shardy, Arman, Mohammed & Mohammed 2015) that good maintenance practice is an attitude which is sadly lacking in Nigeria, whether in the home, office, school or factory.

In this regard the quality and standard of a school is ideally rooted on the provision of sufficiency, operation and supervision of educational facilities. In the same vein, Adejimi, (2015) argued that poorly maintained school building facilities obstruct effective actualization of educational curriculum.

In Bauchi State especially in the suburb areas, most of the school buildings are in shambles. Some of them still wear the look of the 80s (Babayo, 2017). The educational system in Bauchi State and Nigeria alike has witnessed tremendous expansion within the last two decades in the midst of limited school facilities and dilapidated infrastructures (Babayo, 2017).

The effectiveness of schools building maintenance is highly dependent upon the nature of leadership in each school. Most school Principals are characterized by a combination of formal and informal leadership. The school principal is involved in maintenance management, and administrative issues. By implication, the principal of a school is a leader, director, controller, coordinator, organiser, adviser and a maintenance manager (Maduabum, in Lee, Hackman & Scott 2018). The principal implements the set goal and objectives of the school, which of course, must be in line with the national objectives; he/she tasks and allocates responsibilities to the staff according to specialization and expertise (Uyanga, 2008). The school leader and maintenance managers need to solve the problems facing the secondary school, in line with their maintenance responsibilities.

Management of school finance: the managers control the government allocation to the schools. They solicit and get money from the Parents Teachers Association, Alumni Association, Non-Governmental Organizations and

individuals. Provision and maintenance of physical facilities: Principals must be fully concerned with the physical environment and other facilities around the school. Dilapidated buildings, leaking roofs, abandoned projects, overgrown trees and lawns, dingy and dark buildings, have demoralizing effects on people, especially the adolescents (Obidoa, 2006). As a result, the principals have the responsibilities of ensuring that these facilities are in good shape. Even with the little resources at their disposal, they are obliged to provide teachers and other instructional staff with necessary resources for effective teaching (Babayemi, 2006).

Whatever the case, it is the responsibility of the principal as the leader to initiate the process for the maintenance of the school buildings. Building maintenance operation processes require effective interactions between top management (Director Science and Technology and School Administrators) at the strategic level and maintenance personnel (Ministry of Education based Maintenance Officers) at the operational level in order to achieve organizational common goals with better operational performance (Lee, Hackman & Scott 2018).

In providing conducive learning environment technical schools, also called Technical Colleges or Technical Institutes, provide specialized training in a specific career field, trade, or profession, including computer technology, business administration, culinary arts, electronics, medical assisting, legal assisting, automotive technology, and cosmetology among others (Gyang 2015).

Statement of the Problem

Erecting buildings without a functional maintenance plan or policy signal a great danger for the occupant and can lead to serious economic loss. Building school structures with standard materials alongside conscious effort of maintenance make schooling interesting and motivating (Ojara, 2013). However, all technical college buildings are in shambles and deplorable condition. Adenuga and Iyagba (2005) noted that public buildings in Nigeria are in very poor and deplorable conditions of structural and decorative disrepairs. As a result, it has become increasingly difficult to identify a precisely the existing maintenance strategy and options providing solutions in addressing maintenance problems. In addition, there is a paucity of empirical data on the public secondary school buildings and infrastructure. Maintenance program in Nigeria for instance, according to Ahmed (2000) and Odediran Oladele & Eghenure (2012) has not received much attention in the past as the emphasis is on the development of new properties. Furthermore, there is apparent lack of maintenance practice in Nigeria, and that emphasis is placed on the construction of new buildings and neglecting the aspect of maintenance which commences immediately the builder

leaves the site. This is also endorsed by Olagunju (2012) who opined that there is lack of maintenance set up in Nigeria that can sustain the current inadequate housing provision in the country.

However, much is not known and documented on the assessment of the current maintenance practice of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State both in the past and present. In view of the problem statement, it has become necessary to engage on a study that will address current maintenance practice of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State.

Purpose of the Study

The main aim of this study is to find out the current maintenance practice of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State. The study answered the corresponding research question and hypothesis:

1. What is the current maintenance practice of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State?
2. There is no significance difference between the mean responses of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current maintenance practice of Technical College Buildings in Bauchi State.

Methodology

The study used a survey research design. The area of the study was Bauchi State. The target population of the study is made of 31 respondents which comprised all the three school administrators (Principal and Vice Principals) from the eight technical Colleges in Bauchi State, four Engineers (Maintenance Officers), one Directors and two deputy directors Science and Technology of the Bauchi State Ministry of Education. Since the population is manageable, the researcher used total sample population. The instrument for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher based on the extensive review of the literature related to the study. The questionnaire was sub divided into two sections A and B. Section A consist of categories of the respondents. Section B was a questionnaire which was based on the research questions. Five Point Likert type rating Scale of Very Strongly Agreed (VSA)-5 Points, Strongly Agreed (SA)-4 Points, Agreed (A)-3 Points, Strongly Disagreed (SD)-2 Points and Very Strongly Disagreed (VSD)-1 Point was used. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS) version 21 was used to analyse the data that was collected. The decision rule for the hypotheses depends on the calculated P value, when the P value is greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question: What are current maintenance practices of Technical College buildings of Bauchi State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the respondents on current maintenance practices of Technical College buildings.

S/N	Item Statement	N _A =27		N _M =4		X _g	Remark
		X _A	SD _A	X _M	SD _M		
1.	Preventive maintenance	1.81	.786	1.75	.957	1.80	VSD
2.	Corrective maintenance	3.00	.961	2.50	1.000	2.94	Disagree
3.	Planned maintenance	1.56	.506	2.00	0.000	1.62	VSD
4.	Emergency maintenance	2.11	.424	2.00	.816	2.10	VSD
5.	Scheduled maintenance	1.93	.616	1.75	.500	1.91	VSD
6.	Recurring maintenance	1.96	.437	2.25	.500	2.00	Disagree
7.	Predictive maintenance	1.74	.656	1.50	.577	1.71	VSD
8.	Periodic maintenance	1.78	.577	2.00	0.000	1.81	VSD
9.	Shutdown maintenance	1.48	.643	2.00	0.000	1.55	VSD
10.	Deferred maintenance	2.07	.267	2.25	.500	2.09	Disagree
Cluster Mean		1.94		2.00		1.95	

Source: Field Study, 2022

Table 1 shows the Mean and Standard Deviation of the respondents’ responses on the current maintenance practices of Technical College buildings of Bauchi State. The Table showed that cluster mean of 1.94 for Administrators and 2.00 for Maintenance Officers, the grand mean of the respondents is 1.95 and hence Technical Colleges of Bauchi State has no specific maintenance practice.

Hypothesis

There is no significance difference in the mean responses of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current maintenance practices of Technical College buildings.

The result of the independent t-test is presented in Table 2 showed that there no significance difference between the mean response of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current maintenance practices of Technical College buildings within the df of 23, t-value = -0.224, p = .412. Since the p value is greater than the confidence level (P>0.05), the null hypothesis was accepted. Therefore, there is no significance difference in the mean responses of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current maintenance practices of Technical College buildings.

Table 2 t-test analysis of the mean responses of Administrators and Maintenance Officers on the current maintenance practices of Technical College Buildings

	N	X	S.D	Df	T	P	Decision
Administrators	27	1.94	.587				
				23	-0.224	.412	Accepted
Maintenance Officers	4	2.00	.485				

Findings of the Study

The findings of this study show that Technical Colleges of Bauchi State has no particular maintenance practice adopted in the schools in maintaining their building and hence the result of hypothesis was upheld. Hence, there is no significant difference between the mean response of Administrators and maintenance Officers on the current maintenance practices of Technical College Building of Bauchi State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings shows that all the Bauchi State Technical Colleges has no stipulated period allocated for building maintenance, the Technical Colleges has no particular maintenance practice, the popular maintenance carried out in the Technical Colleges is mostly emergency maintenance and that building maintenance is carried out immediately when the need arises in the Technical Colleges of Bauchi. Generally speaking, the findings indicates that all the Technical Colleges of Bauchi State have no specific adopted maintenance practice and hence maintenance is only carried out when the need arise. This finding agrees with the work of Olagunju (2012) who opined that there is lack of maintenance set up in Nigeria that can sustain the current inadequate housing provision in the country and the findings is also in agreement with the work of Tijani, et al (2016) who observed lackadaisical attitude of Nigerians on maintenance practice has negatively affected infrastructural development which is critical and essential to a Nation’s development. Furthermore, the findings agree with the work of Shardy, et al 2015 who noted that good maintenance practice is an attitude which is sadly lacking in Nigeria, whether in the home, office, school or factory.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study, it shows that Bauchi Technical Colleges have no specific maintenance practice adopted for the maintenance of Technical College Buildings and hence the need for the Technical Colleges to adopt a maintenance practice which will help in the maintenance of the College buildings.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study, it is recommended that all Bauchi State Technical Colleges in collaboration with the state Ministry of Education should adopt a specific maintenance practice which will help in the maintenance of the College buildings.

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